

COINAGE IN IMPERIAL SPACE: PS.-ARISTOTLE *OIKONOMIKA* AND THE PLACE OF MONETARY PRODUCTION

ANDREW MEADOWS

THE CONFERENCE FROM WHICH THE PAPERS in this volume emerged carried the rather sweeping title *Coinage in Imperial Space*. The role of coinage within empires has long been a subject of interest, and the Athenians' empire and their apparent attempt to unify coinage within it has loomed large in scholarship on the fifth-century B.C.E.¹ While coinages within the great monarchic empires of the Hellenistic period have been at the centre of a number of recent studies, much work remains to be done.² Our aim in opening a new enquiry was to explore the nature and role of coinage in imperial space across one of the great turning points in history: the conquest of the Achaemenid empire by Alexander the Great. This endeavour, as we shall see, raises multiple questions and involves us in many controversies, but we have an advantage in possessing a contemporaneous theoretical text through which we can interrogate the numismatic evidence. This text has been much discussed in the past. However, what had hitherto been a consensus concerning its approximate date has recently been questioned, its consequences in numismatic terms have never been fully investigated, and the implications of our current understanding of numismatics have not been rigorously applied to its exegesis. So, it seemed time to put this evidence centre-stage and ask some questions about what it and the coinage can tell us.

The text in question survives among the works of Aristotle as the second book of what purports to be an *Oikonomika* in three books. At least since the sixteenth century, the attribution to Aristotle has been rejected, and it also now seems clear that each of the three books was the product of a different author.³ The second, which concerns us here, famously begins with a theoretical analysis

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¹Note, for example, the book-length treatments of Figueira (1998) and Kallet and Kroll (2020).

²For recent synoptic studies, see, for example, Aperghis 2004 and Le Rider and de Callatay 2006; on the Seleucids, see Chankowski and Duyrat 2005; on the Ptolemies, Le Rider and de Callatay 2006 and Olivier forthcoming; and on the Attalids, Thonemann 2013 and Kaye 2022: 129–187.

³Full discussions of the manuscript traditions and modern scholarship can be found in the editions of Book 1 by Victor (1983), Book 2 by van Groningen (1933), and Zoepffel's (2006) translation and commentary of the whole work. Book 3, which is lost and survives only in Latin translation, is probably significantly later in date; see Swain 2013: 28–30. Note too Descat's (2003: 155–156) suggestion that Book 2 (like Book 1?) may have been the work of Aristotle's pupil Theophrastus of Eresos.

of what the author considers to be the four principal types of economy. It then goes on to provide a series of examples of behaviour by which individuals in the past have sought to secure revenues or to successfully administer an economy.

Before moving to a discussion of the context of this crucial work and its significance, it will be fruitful to begin by taking a look at the text of the introduction (wherein the structure of the work and the place of coinage are laid out) and a translation. In certain places this text is certainly defective, while in others it appears to be so. How we fill the lacunae and correct what may appear to us to be wrong depends in part on what we think the author was trying to say, so there is some danger of circularity. I reproduce below, for the most part, the text offered originally by van Groningen⁴ and my own translation, and indicate in the notes some key places where I differ from others in the restoration of the text and in its interpretation.⁵

Ps.-Arist. *Oec.* 2.1.1–8, 1345b7–1346a31:

[1.1] τὸν οἰκονομεῖν μέλλοντά τι κατὰ τρόπον τῶν τε τόπων, περὶ οὗς ἂν πραγματευέται, μὴ ἀπείρωσ ἔχειν, καὶ τῇ φύσει εὐφυῆ εἶναι καὶ τῇ προαιρέσει φιλόπονον τε καὶ δίκαιον· ὅτι γὰρ ἂν ἀπὴ τούτων τῶν μερῶν, πολλὰ διαμαρτήσεται περὶ τὴν πραγματείαν ἂν μεταχειρίζεται. οἰκονομία δέ εἰσι τέσσαρες, ὡς ἐν τύπῳ διελέσθαι (τὰς γὰρ ἄλλας εἰς τοῦτο ἐμπιπτούσας εὐρήσομεν): βασιλική, σατραπική, πολιτική, ἰδιωτική. [1.2] τούτων δὲ μεγίστη μὲν καὶ ἀπλουστάτη ἡ βασιλική, <μεγίστη δὲ καὶ> ποικιλωτάτη <ἢ σατραπική, ἐλαχίστη>⁶ δὲ καὶ ῥάσθη ἢ πολιτική, ἐλαχίστη δὲ καὶ ποικιλωτάτη ἡ ἰδιωτική. ἐπικοινωνεῖν μὲν τὰ πολλὰ ἀλλήλαις ἀναγκαῖόν ἐστιν· ὅσα δὲ μάλιστα δι’ αὐτῶν ἐκάστη συμβαίνει, ταῦτα ἐπισκεπτέον ἡμῖν ἐστιν. πρῶτον μὲν τοῖνον τὴν βασιλικὴν ἴδωμεν. ἔστι δὲ αὕτη δυναμένη μὲν τὸ καθόλου, εἶδη δὲ ἔχουσα τέσσαρα· περὶ <τὸ> νόμισμα, περὶ τὰ ἐξαγώγιμα, περὶ τὰ εἰσαγώγιμα, περὶ τὰ ἀναλώματα. [1.3] τούτων δὲ ἕκαστον. περὶ μὲν τὸ νόμισμα λέγω ποῖον καὶ πότε τίμιον ἢ εὐωνον⁷ ποιητέον, περὶ δὲ τὰ ἐξαγώγιμα καὶ εἰσαγώγιμα πότε καὶ τίνα παρὰ τῶν σατραπῶν ἐν τῇ ταγῇ ἐκλαβόντι αὐτῷ λυσιτελήσει διατίθεται, περὶ δὲ τὰ ἀναλώματα τίνα περιαιρετέον καὶ πότε, καὶ πότερον δοτέον νόμισμα εἰς τὰς

⁴First in van Groningen 1933 and reprinted in van Groningen and Wartelle 1968.

⁵For recent discussion of the nature of the economies and revenues described in this passage, see Descat 2003; Aperghis 2004; and Chankowski 2007; also see above, 3, n. 3.

⁶The restorations here are mine. That something has dropped out of the text is clear enough. See the discussion of van Groningen (1933: *ad loc.*). The required sense seems clear enough too, though that has not often been recognized. The author seems to be constructing a matrix with axes of complexity and size.

	Small (ἐλαχίστη)	Large (μεγίστη)
Simple (ἀπλουστάτη, ῥάσθη)	Civic	Royal
Complex (ποικιλωτάτη)	Individual	Satrapal

Royal is “biggest and simplest”; individual is “smallest and most complex.” “Biggest and most complex” and “smallest and simplest” remain as categories, and these must belong to satrapal and the civic respectively. The source of most modern confusion seems to be that the author uses ἀπλουστάτη and ῥάσθη as synonyms.

⁷Van Groningen suggested the deletion of τίμιον ἢ εὐωνον.

δαπάνας ἢ ἀντὶ νομίσματος⁸ ὄνια. [1.4] δεύτερον δὲ τὴν σατραπικὴν. ἔστι δὲ ταύτης εἶδη ἕξ τῶν προσόδων.⁹ αὐτῶν δὲ τούτων πρώτη μὲν καὶ κρατίστη ἢ ἀπὸ τῆς γῆς, αὕτη δὲ ἔστιν ἂν οἱ μὲν ἐκφόριον, οἱ δὲ δεκάτην προσαγορευουσιν· δευτέρα δὲ ἢ ἀπὸ τῶν ἰδίων γινομένη, οὗ μὲν χρυσίον, οὗ δὲ ἀργύριον, οὗ δὲ χαλκός, οὗ δὲ ὅποσα δύναται γίνεσθαι· τρίτη δὲ καὶ ἢ ἀπὸ τῶν ἐμπορίων· τετάρτη δὲ καὶ ἢ ἀπὸ τῶν κατὰ γῆν τε καὶ ἀγοραίων τελῶν γινομένη· πέμπτη δὲ ἢ ἀπὸ τῶν βοσκημάτων, ἐπικαρπία τε καὶ δεκάτη καλουμένη· ἕκτη δὲ ἢ ἀπὸ τῶν ἀνθρώπων,¹⁰ ἐπικεφάλαιόν τε καὶ χειρωνάξιον προσαγορευομένη. [1.5] τρίτον δὲ τὴν πολιτικὴν. ταύτης δὲ κρατίστη μὲν πρόσδοδος ἢ ἀπὸ τῶν ἰδίων ἐν τῇ χώρᾳ γινομένη· εἶτα ἢ ἀπὸ τῶν ἐμπορίων καὶ διαγωγῶν· εἶτα ἢ ἀπὸ τῶν ἐγκυκλίων. [1.6] τέταρτον δὲ καὶ τελευταῖον τὴν ἰδιωτικὴν. αὕτη δὲ ἔστιν ἀνόματος μὲν διὰ τὸ δεῖν μὴ πρὸς ἕνα σκοπὸν οἰκονομεῖν, ἐλαχίστη δὲ διὰ τὸ καὶ τὰς προσόδους καὶ τὰ ἀναλώματα βραχέα γίνεσθαι. αὕτης δὲ ταύτης κρατίστη μὲν πρόσδοδος ἢ ἀπὸ γῆς γινομένη· δευτέρα δὲ ἢ ἀπὸ τῶν ἄλλων ἐγκλημάτων· τρίτη δὲ ἢ ἀπὸ ἀργυρίου. χωρὶς δὲ τούτων ὁ πάσαις μὲν ἐπικοινωνεῖται ταῖς οἰκονομίαις (καὶ προσήκει σκοπεῖν αὐτὸ μὴ παρέργως), μάλιστα δὲ ταύτη, τὸ ἀναλώματα μὴ μείζω τῶν προσόδων γίνεσθαι. [1.7] ἐπεὶ τοίνυν τὰς διαιρέσεις εἰρήκαμεν, μετὰ τοῦτο πάλιν νοητέον ἡμῖν,¹¹ ἢ σατραπεία, περὶ ἣν ἂν πραγματεύομεθα, ἢ πόλις, πότερον ἂ πάντα ἄρτι διειλόμεθα ἢ τὰ μέγιστα τούτων εἰ δυνατὴ φέροι ἐστί· <εἰ δ' ἐστί> τούτοις χρηστέον· μετὰ δὲ τοῦτο ποῖα τῶν προσόδων ἢ τὸ παράπαν οὐκ εἰσὶ, δυνατὰ δ' εἰσὶ γενέσθαι, ἢ μικρὰ νῦν οὔσαι μείζους οἰαί {τινες} κατασκευασθῆναι, ἢ τῶν ἀναλωμάτων τῶν νῦν ἀναλουμένων, τίνα τε καὶ πόσα περιαιρεθέντα <τὰ> ὅλα μὴθὲν βλάψει. [1.8] τὰ μὲν οὖν περὶ τὰς οἰκονομίας τε καὶ τὰ μέρη τὰ τούτων εἰρήκαμεν· ὅσα δὲ τινες τῶν πρότερον πεπράγασι εἰς πόρον χρημάτων εἴ<τε> τεχνικῶς τι διόκησαν, ἃ ὑπελαμβάνομεν ἀξιόλογα αὐτῶν εἶναι, συναγοράκαμεν. οὐδὲ γὰρ ταύτην τὴν ἱστορίαν ἀχρεῖον ὑπολαμβάνομεν εἶναι. ἔστι γὰρ ὅτε τούτων ἐφαρμόσει τι οἷς ἂν αὐτὸς πραγματεύη.

[1.1] Whoever wants to administer correctly should not be ignorant of the region and should be well-endowed by nature and industrious and just by purpose. For the lack of any one of these will lead to many failures in the task one takes in hand. There are four types of administration (under which all others may be classified), which may be categorized as follows: royal, satrapal, civic, and personal. [1.2] Of these, the royal is the largest and simplest; <the satrapal is the biggest> and most complex; the civic is <the smallest> and simplest; the personal is the smallest and most complex. Inevitably, they overlap with each other in many respects; what is especially characteristic of each, that is what we must examine. We will look first at the royal administration. Its power is overarching and has four categories: concerning coinage, concerning exports, concerning imports, concerning expenditure. [1.3] I will take each of these in turn: I mean for coinage the decision about what kind and when to produce of high or low value; for imports and

⁸ ἢ ἀντὶ νομίσματος is van Groningen's correction of a clearly corrupt set of variant readings in the mss.

⁹ Van Groningen (1933: *ad loc*) excludes here as marginal: ἀπὸ γῆς, ἀπὸ τῶν ἐν τῇ χώρᾳ ἰδίων γινομένων, ἀπὸ ἐμπορίων, ἀπὸ τελῶν, ἀπὸ βοσκημάτων, ἀπὸ τῶν ἄλλων ("from the land, from the special products of the country, from markets, from taxes, from cattle, and from other sources").

¹⁰ The mss here read ἄλλων: for the correction, see van Groningen 1933: *ad loc*.

¹¹ ἡμῖν is silently omitted in van Groningen 1933 and silently returned in van Groningen and Wartelle 1968.

exports, what of the goods that he received from the satraps in their province¹² should be sold for his profit, and when; and for expenditure, what can be cut and when, and whether payment for expenses should be made in coin or in goods in place of coin. [1.4] The second type is the satrapal. It has six categories of revenues. Of these, the first and most important is that from the land (which some call the produce-tax and some the tithe);¹³ the second is that from their personal estates, in some places gold, in others silver, in others copper, and in others whatever can be extracted;¹⁴ third is revenue from the market in foreign goods; fourth is that which arises from taxes on land trade and on market sales;¹⁵ fifth is the revenue from pasturage, called the first-fruits or the tithe; and the sixth, revenue from people, which we term poll-tax, or tax on manufacturing. [1.5] The third type is the civic. The most important revenue of this is that from personal property in the country; then comes that from foreign trade and transit; and then that from farmed taxes.¹⁶ [1.6] Fourth and last is the personal. This is irregular owing to the necessity that it not be administered towards a single aim; and smallest because both revenues and expenses are small. The most important revenue is that which comes from the land; second are those from commerce(?);¹⁷ the third is revenue from money. Apart from these, it is common to all the kinds of administration (and it is best to keep an eye on this assiduously especially for this category), that expenditures should never become greater than revenues. [1.7] Having spoken of the divisions of our subject, we must next again consider whether the satrapy with which we are concerned, or the city, is able to produce all that we have just detailed or at least the biggest of them. If it is, they must be used. Next what kinds of revenue, either now wholly absent, may yet come into being, or now small, may be rendered more abundant, or what and how many items of current expenditure may be reduced without damaging the whole. [1.8] Having spoken thus of administrations and their parts, we have collected such things as we deemed noteworthy that certain men who administered(?) previously did for provision of money, and also of their skill in administration. For we do not think this inquiry lacking in utility, for there may be occasions when we can apply such a lesson to the matters with which we have to deal.

¹²For the translation of *ταγῆ*, see Aperghis 2004: 120–121 and Zoepffel 2006: *ad loc.*

¹³*Pace* Aperghis (2004: 122–123), it does not seem to me that the author is trying to distinguish between two different types of tax here, but rather between two different terms for the same tax.

¹⁴The basic sense of this passage, i.e., that it is referring to mineral resources and their extraction is grasped by Aperghis (2004: 124–125). He confuses matters, however, in his assumption that the owner of τῶν ἰδῶν is the king. Since we are here discussing the satrapal administration, the owner must surely be the satrap (see, for example, Natali [1995: 73], who translates, “*dai domini propri del satrapo*”). Whatever the reality of the situation was on the ground, the assumption of the author is that the satraps owned the mines and derived mineral wealth from them. For attestations of satrapal *idia*, see Tuplin 1987: 134, n. 92.

¹⁵There seems to be a distinction in categories three and four between international trade in the *emporion* and domestic trade in the *agora*; implicitly this is a contrast between sea-borne and land-borne trade, for the most part; however, *pace* Aperghis (2004: 125–126 and 134–135), I do not see that this is explicit and thus useable to date the work. See further below, 7–8.

¹⁶For discussion of the meaning of τῶν ἐγκυκλίων, see Chankowski 2007: 312–313.

¹⁷On the problem of the meaning of ἐγκλημάτων, see van Goningen 1933: *ad loc.* Plainly, we are looking for a source of personal income that is neither agricultural (the most common) or moneylending, etc. (less common). Commerce would seem to be the intended meaning.

Book 2 of the *Oikonomika* is an extraordinary document in a number of respects. It appears to be a short treatise concerned with the correct means of “economics” or “household” administration (*oikonomia*).¹⁸ For this, the author claims, it is important to have knowledge of one’s sphere of activity (τῶν . . . τόπων περὶ οὓς ἂν πραγματευῆται, μὴ ἀπείρως ἔχειν), to have natural ability (τῇ φύσει εὐφυῆ εἶναι), and to be hardworking and just (φιλόπονόν τε καὶ δίκαιον).¹⁹ Doubts have been expressed about the unity of the work, but van Groningen (1933: 37–48) has made a forceful case for its coherence. If one accepts his conclusions, the work consists essentially of two parts (Chapters 2.1.1–6 and 2.2.1–41), connected by a bridging section (2.1.7–8). The first part (1.1–6) begins with a dissection of the four main branches of *oikonomia*. The second (2.1–41) consists of a compendium of *exempla* that illustrate the ways in which various figures can be seen to have acted. These are suitable for adaptation and reuse towards the primary aim of good “economics,” that is, ensuring that expenditures never become greater than revenues (τὸ τὰναλώματα μὴ μείζω τῶν προσόδων γίνεσθαι, 2.1.6, 1346a).

Until recently, scholars seemed to have settled on a date for this text centred around the last quarter of the fourth century B.C.E. or the very beginning of the third, partly on the basis of the style of writing, but crucially also through consideration of the *exempla* that are offered in Part Two of the work.²⁰ A summary of those anecdotes that can be dated makes the picture clear (Fig. 1).

In general, there is a strong preponderance of stories from the fourth century and, moreover, a remarkable concentration of stories concerning contemporaries or subordinates of Alexander the Great, such as Philoxenos the Macedonian (2.2.31, 1351b–1352a), Antimenes of Olynthos (2.2.34a–b, 1352b–1353a; 2.2.38, 1353a), Ophellas of Olynthos (2.2.35, 1353a), and especially Cleomenes of Naucratis (2.2.33a–33f, 1352a–b). There is, however, nothing said about any of the successor generals and kings.

The recent attempt by Aperghis to downdate the text to ca 275 B.C.E. is based essentially on two propositions. The first is that in paragraph 8 the compendium is introduced as ὅσα δέ τινες τῶν πρότερον πεπράγασιν. As Aperghis points out, an aorist participle must be understood with τῶν πρότερον, and he opts for βιοσάντων, yielding the sense “such things as men who lived in the past did . . .” He thus assumes that a generation or more has passed since the last of the exploits listed in the compendium (ca 325/4 B.C.E.), and thus arrives at a date of composition of ca 275 B.C.E. It is equally possible that the verb is describing a function or an action (e.g., ἄγειν, οἰκονομεῖν), meaning only that their actions are earlier than the date of writing. The second proposition is that a supposed distinction between sea-borne and land-borne trade is observable in

¹⁸On the history of the terminology, and the development of the discourse in the fifth and fourth centuries, see Descat 1988.

¹⁹Ps.-Arist. *Oec.* 2.1.1, 1345b.

²⁰See the discussion of van Groningen (above, 3, n. 3); summary in Aperghis 2004: 129, n. 14; and full account in Zoepffel 2006: 214–233 and 529–530.

Fig. 1. Datable *exempla* in ps.-Arist. *Oec.* Book 2.

paragraph 4, and that this points to the existence of inland trading centres such as Seleukeia on the Tigris and Syrian Antioch. The distinction in this paragraph seems to me to be more one between foreign trade conducted in the *emporium* and the local trade of goods from the land taking place in the *agora*, but, in any case, this formulation cannot carry the chronological weight and significance that Aperghis needs to make his argument work.²¹

A date of composition within the last decade or so of the fourth century or in the very early part the third thus seems highly likely.²² This was a world in which the Achaemenid imperial space was being transformed into that of Alexander.²³ What does that world look like? An examination of the geographical distribution of *exempla* also reveals an interesting pattern (Figs. 2–3).

If, for the purposes of illustration, we want to condense this distribution down to areas that formed part of the Achaemenid empire and subsequently entered the empire of Alexander, then we can see that almost 70% (52 out of 76) of the stories in the work are set in the world in which we are interested. This is doubly important, because we thereby perceive not only a period of composition for the work itself, but also the intellectual environment in which it was conceived. This picture is qualitatively confirmed by the identities of the subjects

²¹ See above, 6, n. 15.

²² Though see the discussion of Ellis-Evans and Kagan (below, 217–219) for the suggestion of a more layered composition, reaching its final form in the immediate aftermath of Alexander's conquest.

²³ For an overview of the work's place in the economic thought and the transition from the Achaemenid to the Hellenistic world, see Descat 2006: esp. 364–371.

Fig. 2. Geographical distribution of *exempla* in ps.-Arist. *Oec.* Book 2.

of the anecdotes. We have already noted the marked presence of the officers of Alexander. We can also see that there is a significant presence of representatives of the Persian administration in the persons of Mausolus (2.2.13a–b, 1348a), his hyparch Kondalos (2.2.14a–d, 1348a), Aristoteles of Rhodes, governor of Phokaia²⁴ (2.2.15–b, 1348a–b), Datames (2.2.24a–b, 1350b), Memnon and Mentor of Rhodes (2.2.28–29a, 1351a–b), and Euaisēs(?) the Syrian (2.2.32, 1352a).

That so many of these *exempla* have been drawn from officers operating within imperial space is surely conditioned also by the author's intended audience. He is, in fact, quite explicit about this audience. As he writes in paragraph 7, it is the satrapy about which we are primarily concerned (ἡ σατραπεία, περὶ ἣν ἂν πραγματευώμεθα). This in turn is important in situating the work within a body of literature that emerged in the late fourth century and was concerned with the theory of governance in an expanding world. From a focus on *politeiai* academic interest shifted to *basileia*. In the writings of Xenophon and Plato, for example, we see attempts to rationalize kings and kingdoms as analogous to the master and his household. Plato's young Socrates, when asked in the *Politikos* (259b), "so far as government is concerned, is there any difference between the grandeur of a large house and the majesty of a small city?," cannot see one; "the statesman (*politikos*), king (*basileus*), master (*despotes*), and householder (*oikonomos*) . . . are all one," he agrees (258e); "it is clear that all these are the objects of one

²⁴The precise date of his command there is unclear. Conceivably he was a Hecatomnid appointee: see Zoepffel 2006: 598.

Fig. 3. Heatmap of distribution of *exempla* in ps.-Arist. *Oec.* Book 2.

science (*episteme*), and whether a man calls this the art of kingship (*basilike*) or statesmanship (*politike*) or householding (*oikonomike*), let us not quarrel with him” (259c).²⁵ For Xenophon, the Persian king was analogous to a farmer managing estates,²⁶ or a shepherd.²⁷

However, our text very clearly has a different mode of conceptualization. The kingdom is not one *oikos* with the king as its master. It is a series of overlapping *oikoi*, and the administration of each one is different in detail.²⁸ This change in view of the *basileia* developed, presumably, not so much as the size of kingdoms grew (the Achaemenid kingdom was already immense in Xenophon’s day, and Xenophon was well aware of this), but rather as Greeks took on the role of administrators of this expanse and began to theorize on its administration. In practical terms, since it had previously been possible to theorize the king as master (*despotes*, and our text betrays the vestiges of that notion), and since the lower levels of city and individual were already well understood, inevitably an

²⁵“Τί δέ: μεγάλης σχήμα οικήσεως ἢ σμικρᾶς αὐ πόλεως ὄγκος μὴν τι πρὸς ἀρχὴν διοίσετον”; “τὸν πολιτικὸν καὶ βασιλέα καὶ δεσπότην καὶ ἔτ’ οἰκονόμον θήσομεν ὡς ἓν”; “φανερὸν ὡς ἐπιστήμη μία περὶ πάντ’ ἐστὶ ταῦτα· ταύτην δὲ εἴτε βασιλικὴν εἴτε πολιτικὴν εἴτε οἰκονομικὴν τις ὀνομάζει, μὴδὲν αὐτῷ διαφερόμεθα.”

²⁶Note the famous discussion of the Great King in Xenophon’s *Oikonomikos* (4.4–12). For the extension of the range of the word *οἰκονομία* to the management of larger entities by Xenophon and others, see Pomeroy 1994: 240.

²⁷See *Cyropaedia* 8.2.14 for Cyrus *dictum* that παραπλήσια ἔργα εἶναι νομέως ἀγαθοῦ καὶ βασιλέως ἀγαθοῦ. (“the duties of a good shepherd and of a good king are very similar”). For the concept, see further Attack 2020: 122.

²⁸On this important distinction, see Descat 2006: 365–368. Note also the detailed discussion of the intellectual background to the work in Zoepffel 2006: esp. 118–137.

intermediate level in interest and theorizing opened up in the area that was new to Greek experience, that of the provincial governor. The *Oikonomika* is our first, and perhaps only, example of a work specifically addressed at this cadre, but it is no surprise, intellectually speaking, that it should exist.

There is one further corollary to this direction of attention towards the satrapal economy within this text. When the author divides the different levels into different administrations (*oikonomiai*), he is not conducting a theoretical exercise with the aim of laying out four different *oikonomiai* as separate entities, each interpretable on its own terms. Rather, he is dissecting a complete entity. Although his concern is primarily with one element, the satrapal, this exists within a greater whole: a kingdom. The latter is, as it were, a sealed unit, containing elements that work alongside each other and indeed may overlap in behaviour and functionality. He is, in fact, quite explicit about this: “Inevitably, they overlap with each other in many respects; what is especially characteristic of each, that is what we must examine” (2.1.2, 1345b: ἐπικοινωνεῖν μὲν τὰ πολλὰ ἀλλήλαις ἀναγκαῖόν ἐστιν· ὅσα δὲ μάλιστα δι’ αὐτῶν ἐκάστη συμβαίνει, ταῦτα ἐπισκεπτέον ἡμῖν ἐστιν).

With this in mind, we may focus specifically on the question of coinage, and the role that it plays within our text. If we turn to Part I of the work, we can suggest a fairly clear hypothesis that needs to be tested. As we have seen, this section of the *Oikonomika* divides the spheres of economic activity into four categories: “There are four main types of economies, under which all others may be classified: royal, satrapal, civic, and personal” (2.1.1, 1345b: βασιλική, σατραπική, πολιτική, ἰδιωτική). And just as famously, the author of the *Oikonomika* places the production of coinage within the purview of just one of these categories: the royal.

We will look first at the royal administration. Its power is overarching and has four categories: concerning coinage (νόμισμα), concerning exports, concerning imports, concerning expenditure. Taking each of these in turn, I mean for coinage the decision about what kind and when to produce of high or low value (περὶ . . . τὸ νόμισμα λέγω ποῖον καὶ πότε τίμιον ἢ εὐῶνον ποιητέον);²⁹ for imports and exports, what of the goods that he received from the satraps in their province³⁰ should be sold for his profit, and when; and

²⁹ For the history of the interpretation of this passage, see Zoepffel 2006: 543. The words τίμιον ἢ εὐῶνον are excluded by van Groningen (1933: 31–32) “comme constituant une glose de ποῖον”; cf. van Groningen and Wartelle 1968: 53, n. 4. This seems to me to prejudge the potential import of this statement. The translation offered by Aperghis (2004: 119) as “large or small denomination” seems to me not quite to capture the natural meaning of these words, which are generally used to qualify prices (expensive and cheap). This last interpretation opens up the possibility that the author is here referring to the size of coinage, which is otherwise neglected here. Otherwise the question of quantity must be taken as implicit: see Bresson (2005: 46) in reply to Panagopoulou (2001: 348). For further discussion, see Ellis-Evans and Kagan (below, 214–215), noting the suggestion of John Ma that we might emend πότε <ρον>.

³⁰ For the translation of ταγή, see above, 6, n. 12.

for expenditure, what can be cut and when, and whether payment for expenses should be made in coin or in goods in place of coin.” (2.1.2–3, 1345b)³¹

What is the significance of the fact that coinage appears in just one of the economic categories? As we have noted, the author promises “what is especially characteristic of each, that is what we must examine” (2.1.2, 1345b). That is to say that what the author is specifically highlighting under each of his four headings are the things that separate them and make them distinctive. If we approach the descriptions of the four economies with this in mind, an interesting “balance sheet” emerges:

Royal Economy (2.1.2–3, 1345b)

Expenditure

I mean for coinage the decision about of what kind and when to produce of high or low value; and for expenditure, what can be cut and when, and whether payment for expenses should be made in coin or in goods in place of coin.

Income

for imports and exports, what of the goods that he received from the satraps in their province should be sold for his profit, and when.

Satrapal Economy (2.1.4, 1345b–1346a)

Expenditure

Income

the first and most important is that from the land (which some call the produce-tax and some the tithe);
the second is that from their personal estates, in some places gold, in others silver, in others copper, and in others whatever can be extracted;
third is revenue from the market in foreign goods;
fourth is that which arises from taxes on land trade and on market sales;
fifth is the revenue from pasturage, called the first-fruits or the tithe;
and in the sixth, revenue from people, which we term poll-tax, or tax on manufacturing.

Civic Economy (2.1.5, 1346a)

Expenditure

Income

The most important revenue of this is that from personal property in the country; then comes that from foreign trade and transit; and then that from local taxes.

³¹For the Greek text, see above, 4–5.

Personal Economy (2.1.6, 1346a)

*Expenditure**Income*

The most important revenue is that which comes from the land; second are those from commerce(?);
the third is revenue from money.

It is evident from this tabulation that there is a disparity between expenditure and income in the *Oikonomika's* conceptualization of the economies. At a very basic level, there is a far greater dissection of the different forms of revenues (income) available in the different levels of the economy. The author is trying to give an overview of all those available and distinctive at a series of specific levels, and this results in an inevitable overlap. So, for example, taxes on *emporía* feature in both the satrapal and the civic economies. Both of these also include taxes on agricultural produce and on other forms of extraction or production particular to the region concerned.

Distinctive expenditure, on the other hand, finds a far more simplistic treatment, and occurs only at one level in the economy: the royal. And here, too, we find the sole mention of coinage. Of course, the author could have chosen to include this item under the first three types of economy, and this would indeed correspond to one way in which modern scholars categorise coinage: royal, satrapal, and civic. Or he could have chosen to omit it entirely, since on the modern reading it is common to three of his categories, and thus not especially distinctive. However, by choosing to include it at all, and then to include it only in the royal economy, the author of the *Oikonomika* is firmly suggesting to us that, within the larger body of the imperial state, the decision to produce coinage is distinctive to the royal economy, and lodged at this level and nowhere else.³² If the other economies have expenditure needs (and the entire treatise is predicated on the notion that they do), then it is not ordinarily the role of the satrap, city, or individual to produce the coin to meet that need. We should note that there is no internal inconsistency in the author's position here. His comment on coinage is focused explicitly on its fabrication (*ποιητέον*), and that is the sense in which it is an expenditure. Once that coinage was in circulation, it became a medium by which expenditures could be made, but, since it already existed and was in circulation, in terms of its physical fabrication it did not constitute an expenditure in and of itself. Thus, in the author's world of the late fourth century, all coinage is royal in nature, but not necessarily in use. And this is one of the primary hypotheses that we need to test.

At first sight, and perhaps even at second or third, this sounds like a bold claim. As we have just noted, numismatists are well-accustomed to categorising coinage as "royal," but they also readily use the categories of "satrapal" and

³²Cf. Bresson 2005: 47: "This statement is an implicit indication that minting was closely linked to state expenditure."

“civic” when defining the perceived authorities and agencies behind a coinage. Nonetheless, there are reasons to take such a claim from an apparently contemporary author seriously.

We should begin by testing it in ps.-Aristotle’s text. In the second part of his book, he preserves a series of anecdotes designed to guide the administrator of the economy. This is prefaced by the explanation: “Having spoken thus of administrations and their parts, we have collected such things as we deemed noteworthy that certain men who administered(?) previously did for provision of money, and also of their skill in administration” (2.1.8, 1346a25–27). There ought to be some place for coinage among these *exempla*, and, indeed, we find it in seven of the anecdotes he relates. None of them is straightforwardly royal, and so they might seem to run counter to the impression given by the analysis of economies; but, in fact, I would suggest, they strengthen it.

Three of these cases are examples that come close to being royal, since they involve tyrants. First, there is the story of the Athenian Hippias and how

he declared the coinage of Athens *adokimos* (“unacceptable”) and having declared a price for it ordered the people to bring it in to him; and when they came to receive the newly minted coin, he simply handed back the same coins as before.³³

We should note in this case both the status of Hippias at Athens (a tyrant, thus effectively a monarch, not a magistrate, and therefore a suitable *exemplum*) and the fact that he did not actually issue coinage. This was sleight of hand.

Second and third, there are two anecdotes related about Dionysius, the tyrant of Syracuse, again an individual who sits above the level of city or governor, though he does not qualify for the designation *basileus*. The second of these two examples records not a straightforward case of an issue of coin, but rather a significant “defrauding” of the people through an enforced reduction in weight standard:

Having borrowed money from the citizens, promising to repay it, when they demanded its return, he bade each bring him, under pain of death, whatever silver he possessed. This silver when brought he coined into drachmae each bearing the face value of two: with these he repaid the previous debt <and also> what had just been brought in.³⁴

The former similarly records a fraud perpetrated by the introduction of base metal coin then forced to pass as precious:

³³ *Oec.* 2.2.4, 1347a4–17: τό τε νόμισμα τὸ δὴ Ἀθηναίους ἀδόκιμον ἐποίησε, τάξας δὲ τιμὴν ἐκέλευσε πρὸς αὐτὸν ἀνακομίζειν· συνελθόντων δὲ ἐπὶ τῷ κόψαι ἕτερον χαρακτῆρα, ἐξέδωκε τὸ αὐτὸ ἀργύριον.

³⁴ *Oec.* 2.2.20h, 1349b27–33: δανεισάμενός τε παρὰ τῶν πολιτῶν χρήματα ἐπ’ ἀποδόσει, ὡς ἀπήτουν αὐτόν, ἐκέλευσεν ἀναφέρειν ὅσον ἔχει τις ἀργύριον πρὸς αὐτόν· εἰ δὲ μή, θάνατον ἔταξε τὸ ἐπιτίμιον. ἀνενεχθέντος δὲ τοῦ ἀργυρίου, ἐπικόψας χαρακτῆρα ἐξέδωκε τὴν δραχμὴν δύο δυναμένην δραχμᾶς καὶ τό τε ὀφειλόμενον πρότερον <...> ἀνήνεγκαν πρὸς αὐτόν.

Dionysius . . . being short of silver minted a coinage of tin, and summoning a public assembly, spoke at length in its favour. The citizens voted, albeit unwillingly, that everyone should regard as silver, and not as tin, whatever he received.³⁵

Fourth, and akin to the last, there is the Athenian general Timotheus and his recourse to base metal coin in a time of crisis. In this case, Timotheus was short of silver coinage (which would have been supplied to him by the mint of Athens), and so was forced to improvise with a local production of bronze:

Timotheus of Athens during his campaign against Olynthus was short of silver and issued to his men a copper coinage instead. On their complaining, he told them that all the merchants and retailers would accept it in lieu of silver. But the merchants he instructed to buy in turn with the copper they received such produce of the land as was for sale, as well as any booty brought to them; such copper as remained on their hands he would exchange for silver.³⁶

Like Dionysius' purported tin coinage, we might note, this is a subversion of the norm in a time of crisis, not a normal state of affairs. But, *mutatis mutandis*, it is in fact a perfect illustration of how coinage would operate within the author's royal economy and those that sat below it. The decision of what kind of coinage should be struck and what its value should be is taken at the top of the pyramid, and the expense of producing it would have been Timotheus'. A variant version of the story even adds that he applied his own badge (*sphragis*) to the coinage.³⁷ Its use further down the pyramid was envisaged and enforced by the "ruler," but this was a question of use, not one of production or expenditure.

Exactly the same circumstance underlies the fifth example, that of the Clazomenaens who,

owing their mercenaries twenty talents of pay and being unable to find it, were giving the leaders of the troop four talents of interest each year. But failing to reduce the capital debt, and committed to this fruitless drain on their revenue, they struck an iron coinage of twenty talents, bearing the face-value of the silver. This they distributed proportionately among the wealthiest citizens and received from them silver to the same amount. Through this expedient, the private citizens possessed a currency which was good for their daily needs, and the state was relieved of its debt. Next, they proceeded

³⁵ *Oec.* 2.2.20c, 1349a32–36: οὐκ εὐπορῶν δὲ ἀργυρίου νόμισμα ἔκοψε καττιτέρου, καὶ συναγαγὼν ἐκκλησίαν πολλὰ τοῦ κεκομμένου νομίσματος ὑπερέειπεν· οἱ δὲ ἐψηφίσαντο καὶ μὴ βουλόμενοι ἕκαστος δ' ἂν εἴλετο ἔχειν ὡς ἀργυροῦν ἀλλὰ μὴ καττιτέρινον.

³⁶ *Oec.* 2.2.23a, 1350a23–30: Τιμόθεος Ἀθηναῖος πολεμῶν πρὸς Ὀλυνθίους καὶ ἀπορούμενος ἀργυρίου, κόψας χαλκὸν διεδίδου τοῖς στρατιώταις· ἀγανακτούντων δὲ τῶν στρατιωτῶν ἔφη αὐτοῖς τοὺς ἐμπόρους τε καὶ ἀγοραῖους ἅπαντα ὡσαύτως πωλήσειν· τοῖς δ' ἐμπόροις προεῖπεν, ὃν ἂν τις λάβῃ χαλκόν, τοῦτου πάλιν ἀγοράζειν τὰ τ' ἐκ τῆς χώρας ὄνια καὶ τὰ ἐκ τῶν λειῶν ἀγόμενα· ὃς δ' ἂν περιλειφθῇ αὐτοῖς χαλκός, πρὸς αὐτὸν ἀναφέροντας ἀργύριον λαμβάνειν.

³⁷ Polyæn. *Strat.* 3.10.1. For the various traditions and the identification of the coinage itself, see Sheedy 2015 and Sheedy *et al.* 2015.

to pay interest out of revenue to those who had advanced the silver; and little by little distributed repayment among them, recalling at the same time the currency of iron.³⁸

The sixth case, that of Byzantium, does not in fact involve the production of coinage at all, but rather the sale of rights to buy and sell coinage in the city:

The people of Byzantium, being in need of funds . . . sold the right of changing money to a single bank, whose proprietor was given a monopoly of the sale and purchase of coin, protected under penalty of confiscation.³⁹

In short, in all the cases where an issuer of a coin is not an individual in position of overall power, the point of the inclusion of the anecdote seems to be focused rather on the question of crisis-management, and so employable by a king should he have the need. None of these anecdotes suggest a normal need for the production of coinage anywhere in economies other than the royal.

Only in the seventh and final story, that of the Persian Datames, do we find normative behaviour being established (and used as a pretext):

Datames the Persian was able to provide for the daily needs of his mercenaries from the enemy's country; but had no coin (νόμισμα) to give them. When their pay became due, and they demanded it, he had recourse to the following trick. He called a meeting and told the men that he had plenty of money, but that it was stored in a certain fortress, which he named. He then broke up his encampment and marched in that direction. On reaching the neighbourhood of the fortress, he himself went on ahead, and entering the place seized all the silver vessels in the temples. He then loaded his mules in such a way that this plate was exposed, thus suggesting that silver formed the entire load; and so continued his march. The soldiers, seeing the plate and supposing that they were conveying a full load of silver, were cheered by the expectation of their pay. They were informed however by Datames that they would have to take it to Amisus to be coined—a journey of many days, and in the winter season. And during all this time, he continued to employ the army without giving it more than its necessary rations.⁴⁰

³⁸ *Oec.* 2.2.16b, 1348b22–32: ὀφειλοντές στρατιώταις μισθὸν εἴκοσι τάλαντα καὶ οὐ δοῦναι δυνάμενοι τόκον ἔφεροντοῖς ἡγεμόσι τέτταρα τάλαντα τοῦ ἐνιαυτοῦ· ἐπεὶ δὲ τοῦ μὲν ἀρχαίου ἀπέκοπτον οὐθέν, αἰεὶ δὲ μάλιστα ἐδαπάνων, νόμισμα ἔκοψαν σιδηροῦν εἰς ἀργυρίου λόγον εἴκοσι τάλαντων, εἶτα διδόντες τοῖς εὐπορωτάτοις ἐν τῇ πόλει κατὰ λόγον ἐκάστω ἀργύριον παρ' ἐκείνων ἔλαβον ἴσον. οἳ τε οὖν ἰδιώται εἶχον εἰς τὰς καθ' ἡμέραν χρείας ἀναλίσκειν καὶ ἡ πόλις τοῦ χρέους ἀπηλλάγη. δεῦτερον δὲ ἐκ τῶν προσόδων ἐκείνοις τὸν τε τόκον κατέφερον καὶ αἰεὶ διαιροῦντες ἐκάστω πρὸς μέρος διεδίδουσαν, τοὺς δὲ σιδηροὺς ἐκομίζοντο. Dengate (1967: 180, n. 48) notes that there is a fourth century silver coinage that might have been part of this process. There is no trace, however, of the iron.

³⁹ *Oec.* 2.2.3a, 1346b13–26: Βυζάντιοι δὲ δεηθέντες χρημάτων . . . τῶν τε νομισμάτων τὴν καταλλαγὴν ἀπέδοντο μὴ τραπέζῃ, ἐτέρω δὲ οὐκ ἦν οὐθενὶ οὔτε ἀποδόσθαι ἐτέρω οὔτε πρίασθαι παρ' ἐτέρου· εἰ δὲ μὴ, στήρησις ἦν. For discussion, see now Russell 2017: 98–104.

⁴⁰ *Oec.* 2.2.24, 1350b16–30: Δατάμης Πέρσης ἔχων στρατιώτας τὰ μὲν καθ' ἡμέραν πορίζεν ἐδύνατο ἐκ τῆς πολεμίας αὐτοῖς, νόμισμα δὲ οὐκ ἔχων διδόναι, ἀπαιτούμενος δέ, χρόνου γενομένου οὐ ᾄφειλε, τεχνάζει τοιόνδε. ἐκκλησίαν συναγαγὼν ἔφη οὐκ ἀπορεῖσθαι χρημάτων, ἀλλ' εἶναι αὐτῷ ἐν χωρίῳ τινί, λέγων ἐν ᾧ εἴη. καὶ ἀναζεύξας ἐβάδιζεν ἐπ' αὐτό· εἶτα, ὡς ἐγγὺς τοῦ χωρίου ἐγένετο, προελθὼν εἰς αὐτὸ ἔλαβεν ἐκ τῶν ἐνότων ἱερῶν ὅσος ἐνήνη κοίλος ἄργυρος· εἶτ'

The success of this ruse depends on two key factors: first, the desire of the mercenaries to receive officially produced coin in payment, and not just silver plate; and second, their belief in the idea that this could only be produced at an administrative centre. Datames could not simply strike coin at will. In this story, therefore, we find clear confirmation of the *Oikonomika's* claim that the production of coinage belongs at a particular point in the economic hierarchy of empire.

But still, we might ask, can it really be that simple? Do we not have lots of coinage within imperial space that is not royal, but rather satrapal or civic? Is it really the case that coins were not minted lower down in the pyramid at the satrapal, civic, and individual levels, but rather that the coinage produced within the royal economy served the purposes of monetary circulation within the other (ideally well-balanced) economies?

These are the questions that we have sought to address in this collection of essays. The picture, I would suggest, may not be quite as simple as it might first seem. In recent years the notion of what a “civic” coinage consists of has come under some scrutiny. If we jump forward to the early first century, it is instructive to focus on the events of the war between Mithridates VI and Rome. In a series of studies, François de Callatay has painted for us a picture of a number of civic coinages that are not what they seem. The silver didrachms of the Aenianes and Leucas, together with the well-known cases of the tetradrachms of Thasos and Maroneia and some of the Athenian New Style coinage, may all now be attributed to Roman rather than local agency.⁴¹ In the first two cases and the last, production can be linked convincingly to the military campaign of Sulla. The relevance of this to us is two-fold. First, we see that coinages that have the appearance of civic issues may be nothing of the sort. They may have been produced in the city they name, but the silver bullion could be the property of the imperial power, and its production authorised by a quasi-monarchical figure such as Sulla. Second, these coins were produced for a specific military purpose.

This “pseudo-civic” production may be a far from isolated phenomenon and have begun much earlier than the first century B.C.E. There has long been suspicion about the nature of the so-called “wreathed issues” of second-century western Asia Minor. Here the quantities of coinage produced, in some cases by

ἐπισκευάσας τὰς ἡμιόλους ὡς ἀγούσας ἀργύριον παρα φαινούσας τε ταῦτα ἐβάδιζεν. ἰδόντες δὲ οἱ στρατιῶται καὶ νομίσαντες ἅπαντα εἶναι ἄργυρον τὰ ἀγόμενα, ἐθάρρησαν ὡς κομιούμενοι τὸν μισθόν. ὁ δὲ ἔφη δεῖν εἰς Ἄμισόν ἐλθόντας ἐπισημήνασθαι. ἦν δ' εἰς τὴν Ἄμισόν ὁδὸς πολλῶν τε ἡμερῶν καὶ χειμέριος· τὸν δὴ χρόνον τοῦτον ἀπεχρᾶτο τῷ στρατοπέδῳ τὰ ἐπιτήδεια μόνον διδοῦς. The episode, which is recorded also by Polyaeus at *Strat.* 7.21.1, probably belongs to Datames' Paphlagonian campaign of 368/7 B.C.E. See Sekunda 1988: 45–46 for discussion. Although coinage signed and struck by Datames is known from Sinope (see Harrison 1982: 164 and 256–265), none has yet been identified from Amisos. For further discussion, see de Callatay (below, 52–53).

⁴¹ See the overview provided by de Callatay 2011 and, for example, 2004 for the case of Leucas and the Aenianes.

cities that had never or barely produced coinage before, are startling.⁴² I have suggested, furthermore, that we may push this pseudo-civic phenomenon back into the third century in the case of, for example, the “autonomous” issues normally attributed to the city of Side in Pamphylia, or the so-called “Pamphylian Alexanders.” A further twist to the story may be added by reconsideration of the posthumous Alexander coinages of western Asia Minor, which are normally taken to be civic in nature, but which, in many cases can be regarded as Seleucid issues.⁴³ They were Seleucid, that is, in the sense that they were struck with royal silver, for royal purposes; there is no reason to doubt that they were struck where they claimed to be. In these cases, we can push the phenomenon back at least as far as 280 B.C.E. How much earlier can we trace pseudo-civic coinage? An obvious fourth-century comparison is the Athenian owl, struck in large quantities in the Persian empire in the Levant and Egypt.⁴⁴ This is not quite the same phenomenon, since it was not struck where it claimed to be; but it nonetheless alerts us to the fact that we cannot trust such statements of origin to tell us whose silver was being struck, or to whom it was being paid.

If we set aside Athens, are there still cases of real pseudo-civic issues in the Achaemenid empire in the fifth and fourth centuries? To take one obvious case for consideration, we might think about the city of Byzantium, which, as we have seen, drew the attention of the author of *Oikonomika* Book 2, and which struck no silver coinage that we can identify for much of the fifth century B.C.E. During the fourth century, by contrast, Byzantium began to produce a silver coinage, first on the Chian standard, and then on the Persian, of colossal size (Fig. 4).

	n	d	D	YOAD
Chian tetradrs (360–340 B.C.E.)	63	52	230 ± 56	40
Chian drs (360–340 B.C.E.)	45	33	98 ± 22	4
Chian hemidrs (360–340 B.C.E.)	108	93	507 ± 107	10
Persian drs (340–320 B.C.E.)	239	209	1188 ± 172	76
Persian hemidrs (340–320 B.C.E.)	359	309	1630 ± 184	52
Persian trihemioib (340–320 B.C.E.)	53	47	308 ± 104	5

Fig. 4. Output of the Byzantine mint, ca 360–320 B.C.E.⁴⁵

⁴²See most recently Psoma 2013 and de Callatay 2013. Suspicion is heightened by the curious pattern of their distribution, largely in Syria: see Duyrat 2016: 374–379.

⁴³See Meadows 2006, 2009, 2015, and 2019.

⁴⁴For an overview, see Van Alfen 2011.

⁴⁵n = number of specimens; d = number of obverse dies observed; D = estimated original number of obverse dies using the method of Carter 1983. For the principle of the YOAD (“Yearly number of Obverse dies in Attic Drachms”), see de Callatay, below, 48. The figures assumed here are Attic drachm 4.35g; Chian tetradrachm 15.35g, drachm 3.70g, hemidrachm 1.85g; Persian drachm

Fig. 5. Annual obverse die use (Attic weight equivalent) by selected producers, 5th–4th cent. B.C.E.⁴⁶

Indeed, at times during the fourth century, Byzantium was perhaps not only the most active mint in the world, but also one of the most active mints the world had ever seen, consuming, most probably, well over 100 Attic drachm-die equivalents per annum. We may set that in context by comparing some other coinages of the fifth and fourth centuries B.C.E. (Fig. 5).

The only other minting entities that are in the same range as Byzantium are Athens at the time it was building its empire and Syracuse when it was fighting the Carthaginians. The satraps of Caria do not even come close. Were the needs of the *polis* of Byzantium really of the same order as those of imperial Athens at its height? Or is there something else behind this coinage?

In his paper below (45–69), de Callatay expands his principle of “too big to be civic” and argues persuasively that a whole series of coinages from southern Asia Minor traditionally identified as civic should in fact be regarded as “supra-civic” in origin, and perhaps be connected with expenditure related to the Persian fleet. Byzantium seems an obviously similar example. And if we can identify one, how many more imperial coinages lie out there disguised as civic issues? Do we need to completely re-evaluate the nature of coin production and use within the Achaemenid imperial space?

If de Callatay is correct, then his conclusions firmly move the decision to issue coin (and of what kind and what value) out of the realm of the civic economy. One might counter that this moves it up only one level to that of

5.60g, hemidrachm 2.80g, trihemiobol 1.40g. Figures are taken from the die-study of Schönert-Geiss (1970) via de Callatay (2003: nos. 117–122). The chronology has been adjusted to reflect the conclusions of Le Rider (1963).

⁴⁶Die estimates taken from de Callatay 2003.

the satrap or *karanos*, but we should also remember the explanation offered by Pharnabazos for his delay in taking military action against Egypt in the 370s B.C.E.: “that he was the master of his words, but the king was the master of his actions.”⁴⁷ This raises the thorny question of whether there was a coinage that can properly be described as satrapal. It may have been Pharnabazos’ (or others’) names that appeared on these coins, but the decision that necessitated their production came from the king.

This might seem like a fine distinction, but in fact it goes to the heart of a bigger administrative question: that of who, in fact, paid Achaemenid troops. Famously, Xenophon makes Cyrus the Great state “I have decided to send satraps to govern the people, receive the tribute, give pay to the garrisons, and attend to any other business that needs attention.”⁴⁸ But this only takes us part of the way. As has been emphasised in the past, the passage creates a link between the tribute and military pay.⁴⁹ No one would doubt that the tribute was set by the king, belonged to the king, and was accounted for to the king by his satraps. Therefore, the *misthos*, as an element deducted from that tribute, logically was also a matter of royal decision. What Xenophon is thus saying in this passage is that the satrap was responsible for making the payments, i.e., administering the *misthos*, but that the decision of what to give (what was deducted from the tribute) was that of the king. This view in fact dovetails well with what else Xenophon has to tell us about the king’s role in military administration. In the famous account in the *Oikonomikos*, he begins, “of all of the countries from which he receives tribute, he gives orders to the ruler concerning how many horsemen, archers, slingers and light-infantry to whom it is necessary to supply provisions . . .”⁵⁰ And he then goes on to explain at length a system of audit of the numbers and quality of troops and garrisons. The key points once again are that it is the king who decides on the level of expenditure, and that there is a clear link in Xenophon’s mind between the income from tribute and the expenditure on the military (λαμβάνει . . . διδόναι).

Of course, the question about military pay is directly analogous to that about coinage, and the similarity may be crystalized by asking the simple question in both cases, “whose bullion lay behind it?” The author of the *Oikonomika* clearly thought that the answer was “the king’s,” and nothing in Xenophon’s testimony concerning the operations of the Achaemenid state in either the *Cyropaedia* or the *Oikonomikos* seems to contradict this.

⁴⁷ Diod. Sic. 15.41.2: τῶν μὲν λόγων αὐτὸς κύριός ἐστι, τῶν δ’ ἔργων ὁ βασιλεὺς.

⁴⁸ Xen. Cyr. 8.6.3: σατράπας πέμψαι μοι δοκεῖ, οἵτινες ἄρξουσιν τῶν ἐνοικούντων καὶ τὸν δασμὸν λαμβάνοντες τοῖς τε φρουροῖς δάσουσι μισθὸν καὶ ἄλλο τελοῦσιν ὅ τι ἂν δέη.

⁴⁹ See Tuplin’s (1987: 171) assertion that “the *misthos* is therefore a charge on the provincial tribute.”

⁵⁰ Xen. Oec. 4.5: ἐξ ὀπόσων περ ἔθνῶν δασμοὺς λαμβάνει <τι>, τέταχε τῷ ἄρχοντι ἐκάστω, εἰς ὀπόσους δεῖ διδόναι τροφήν ἰπέας καὶ τοξότας καὶ σφενδονήτας καὶ γεροφόρους . . .

Fig. 6. Asia Minor hoards, ca

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As we have already seen, *Oikonomika* Book 2 stands at the cusp of Achaemenid and Macedonian rule, and as we discussed at length at the conference, it is necessary to consider what happened next and whether the Macedonian conquest marked a period of massive change in the monetary administration of large imperial territories. Two charts allow us to bridge the gap, but also force us to think about things not just from the production side of coinage, but also from the point of view of its use, that is to say the experience of the inhabitants of this imperial space. The first of these (Fig. 6) tracks the changing weight standards of Western Asia Minor from ca 400 B.C.E. down to the arrival of Alexander, as seen in the hoard evidence. Hoards are listed on the horizontal axis, while the vertical axis presents the number of mints present in each hoard, with their weight standards distinguished by shading.⁵¹

There is a clear shift over time, from a pattern of disunity to a unification in the Chian weight standard (in solid black) during the fourth century B.C.E.⁵² The same graph, extended for the first century after Alexander's conquest looks very different (Fig. 7). There has been a sudden and complete transformation. The Chian weight standard has largely vanished, to be replaced by an almost complete dominance of the Attic standard.⁵³ But the question is why? It seems obvious that this is the result of a decision taken at the royal level to introduce the Attic standard for the production of royal silver, a decision that fits ps.-Aristotle's paradigm perfectly. But where has all the civic coinage gone? And why? Did cities just give up producing coins on their own weight standard? Did they no longer need to produce coins? Or were they never producing them in the first place? Has one royal system simply been replaced by another?

Turning back to the fourth century B.C.E., how do we explain the coalescence after 387 B.C.E. on the Chian standard? Is this a bottom-up phenomenon, driven by civic administrative decisions—precisely what ps.-Aristotle does not suggest was the case? Or was this a top-down phenomenon, driven by the fact that the royal administration took the decision to move to the Chian standard for its own coinage (Figs. 8a and b),⁵⁴ and employed this for a series of pseudo-civic coinages at its newly conquered western fringe? The latter is surely what the *Oikonomika* would suggest to us.

The conference agenda thus laid down a big challenge, and here I have been able only to outline the large-scale problem that faces us and the different approaches we may take. By focusing on the upper level of the economy, as

⁵¹ Hoards are numbered according to Thompson *et al.* 1973 or the inventory in the publication *Coin Hoards*.

⁵² For analysis, see Meadows 2011. Fig. 6 here should be used in place of Fig. 10 there (which is misprinted).

⁵³ For analysis, see Meadows 2021. Fig. 7 here appears there as Fig. 7.

⁵⁴ For discussion, see Meadows in Ashton *et al.* 2002: 210–212. See further Bodzek (below, 70–121), who doubts their royal nature, preferring to see the impetus for the horseman type as Hecatomnid. I doubt, however, that their fabric is Carian.

Figs. 8a and b. Achaemenid silver tetradrachms on the Chian standard, mint of Sardis(?), mid-fourth cent. B.C.E.⁵⁵

defined in the *Oikonomika*, and on the production side of relatively high-value silver coinages, I have highlighted just one aspect of the problem. The coinages I have mentioned are unlikely to have penetrated down to the lowest levels of society. Nor do they represent the full range of production: fractions and bronze coinage present a fundamentally different problem. I have hinted that the so-called satrapal coinages may not be what they seem at all. And we must ask whether the absence of coin-production from ps.-Aristotle's articulation of the three lower levels of the economy conforms to an ancient reality at those levels. This is a question not just about coin production, but also about the impact of coin production or its absence on monetary practices in general. And above all we must acknowledge that the answers to these questions will be geographically and culturally relative. Whoever ps.-Aristotle was, he was certainly Greek, whereas the Achaemenid and Alexander's imperial space was predominantly not.

The papers that follow approach the problems raised by the *Oikonomika* from a number of different perspectives. Van Alfen (32–44) offers an alternative mode of thinking about the reasons for the production of coinage. Arguing for a political interpretation, he sees the early Persian royal coinage, particularly the darics, as functioning within a political economy of royal benefactions. The absence of such motivation in the ps.-Aristotelian *Oikonomika*, on his reading, is due to this work's primarily economic focus (the balancing of income and expenditure). But what emerges from this reading is certainly that the *Oikonomika* author's claim that coinage exists within a royal (political) economy is justified. And uncomfortable though we may be with the idea that coinage was made simply to be given away, the concept of gift-giving was certainly associated with the king by fourth-century Greeks such as Xenophon.⁵⁶

Turning to the second period of transition, from the brief empire of Alexander to the kingdoms of the Successors, we can see that the role of the king was fundamental in the monetary sphere. Olbrycht (275–287) makes a strong case for the involvement of Alexander himself in the creation of the famous "Poros" coinage. As Dahmen (288–299) points out, the Successors were then relatively

⁵⁵ Classical Numismatic Group 102 (2016) 648 and Triton XI (2008) 261.

⁵⁶ See, for example, Xen. *Oec.* 4.4.7, 4.4.15–16.

slow to insert themselves into the appearance of the coinage, preferring rather to allow the continuity of Alexander's monarchic position to be maintained, while the institution of monarchy also provided the vehicle for Alexander's own gradual appearance on the coinage. Everything about the subsequent royal coinage hinged, as our modern name for it suggests, on its royal appearance. For this coinage, royal title was paramount. Yet, one should also note that the conquest of Asia Minor by Alexander effectively destroyed civic coinage for a century. In this sense, the author of the *Oikonomika* might give us the impression of prescience. But it was a prescience based on the powerful dominance of the Great King's empire in his own day that he had no reason to think might change.⁵⁷

Descending from the tip of the pyramid to its base, Duyrat in her study of documentary and hoard evidence from Samaria and Idumaea (228–249) reveals an economy of fully mixed nature. On the one hand, we seem to find the centralized accumulation and disbursement of agricultural produce, potentially as part of the operation of the Achaemenid imperial bureaucracy. Alongside this there is a much more limited appearance of silver in the documents, particularly in Idumaea. On the other hand, some archaeological evidence, restricted though it may be, suggests a world where coinage may be integrated into a system adapted to the use of weighed amounts of silver to make payments. In other words, one might suggest that there is no monopoly of coinage, nor, strictly speaking, any need for it. Coinage that happens to exist is incorporated into a local economy, when necessary, alongside silver in other forms.

Patterns of production may have an impact on practice. Gitler and Tal (250–260) summarise the evidence for the production of coinage in the regions of Samaria, Philistia, Idumaea, and Judaea in the fourth century B.C.E., and perhaps slightly later. All four areas produced a wide variety of fractional coinage down to the conquest by Alexander. Coinage in the first three of these areas may have ceased with the conquest (although Gitler and Tal argue that hoard evidence suggests a continuation of production), but Judaea certainly continued to produce a local form of coinage without cessation throughout the turbulent period of the wars of the Successors. If one could show that this marked the continuation of a locally authorised coinage, then this instance would represent an almost unique survival of a non-royal coinage from the Persian empire into the Hellenistic period. Unfortunately, we simply cannot say who was responsible for the production of this coinage, and a later incarnation of it bears the head of Ptolemy I, providing a salutary warning that royal agency might well be present.⁵⁸

⁵⁷ On the death of civic coinage and its relationship to the *Oikonomika*, see further Meadows 2021.

⁵⁸ For discussion of the dating of the Judaeian issues based on recent hoard evidence, see also Gitler, Lorber, and Fontanille 2016. For the issues with Ptolemaic portrait, see Gitler and Lorber 2006.

Cyprus provides a doubly interesting case, outlined by Markou (261–274). On the one hand, it sits outside the conceptual framework of the *Oikonomika* within the Achaemenid period, since it was apparently never under the control of a satrap, and since it is unlikely that the urban centres of its kingdoms can be regarded straightforwardly as *poleis*.⁵⁹ But at the same time, they conform to the basic tenet of the *Oikonomika* in that the production of coinage on the island seems to sit with the kings before the arrival of Alexander, and then to move into the realm of imperial royal coinage after the Macedonian conquest. Very quickly, local coin production on the island is overtaken first by Alexandrine and then by Antigonid and Ptolemaic royal coinages.⁶⁰

Psoma (146–177) examines an episode of numismatic production that exists in opposition to the Persian paradigm, whether we date it, as she suggests, in the 390s, or in the last few years of the fifth century, as I would prefer.⁶¹ However, the ΣΥΝ coinages, whether we think they belong to Lysander's *symmachia* or Agesilaos', arguably embody an imperialistic approach to coinage. These coinages were struck within a period of Spartan hegemony and recognize that fact in their choice of obverse type. On Psoma's reading, these were produced to fund the Spartan king Agesilaos' operations, and in this sense perform the function of what in the Hellenistic period we would recognize as a royal coinage. Indeed, we might think of them as a forerunner to precisely that phenomenon. They adopt a common type and weight standard, both dictated by their political environment rather than their individual *polis* contexts, though they advertise their place of production by assuming the *parasema* of the cities concerned, like the mintmarks of later royal coinage. We have not reached the period of the *Oikonomika*, but the conceptual model of a royal coinage with multiple, identifiable locations of production is emerging, and the king (or Lysander) is calling the shots.

In one very simple sense, the association of the king with coinage in the Achaemenid period was clearly strong. This association on a metaphorical level is clearly brought out by Tuplin (122–145) in his discussion of the gold daric and the Aryandic silver. Herodotus thought the former to be Darius' *mnēmosunon* (4.166). In this he may be referring to the name the Greeks gave the coins, but he may equally be responding to the very heavy hint the Persians added to darics and sigloi in the form of the representation of a crowned figure on the obverse. The overbearing presence of the king on other coinages, or at least a Greek perception of this, is perhaps in evidence on other Achaemenid coinages in Cilicia. In the third part of his paper, Tuplin suggests that this may have been the motive behind the curious hybridity observable in the famous winged-

⁵⁹ See Maier 2004: 1224: "There is no positive evidence either for the inhabitants of the cities being citizens and not subjects, or for the development of representative institutions before the end of C4."

⁶⁰ For the Alexandrine, see Markou 2019.

⁶¹ See Meadows 2011.

disk coinage of Tiribazus. As Tuplin stresses, a certainty of interpretation is impossible here, as it is on several similarly hybrid coin designs from Cilicia and Transeuphratene. But one might add that many of these designs adapt images of royal power from the Achaemenid repertoire, while responding also to an apparent Greek preference to see a deity as guarantor of the coinage with which they were paid. One can certainly see how, from observing a daric or a siglos or an issue of Tiribazus, a Greek observer might take the nature of coinage to be royal.

Bodzek (70–121) tackles head-on the question of “satrapal coinage.” The *Oikonomika*, as we have seen, addresses itself directly to the would-be satrap, but denies the existence of a distinctive coinage function at that level of the economy. Are there really satrapal coins, or are these royal coinages in satrapal guise, and therefore pseudo-satrapal? For him, the legends and iconography that apparently identify satrapal, dynastic, or karanic agency in the production of coinage are sufficient to warrant characterisation as such. While this is a defensible position, it still leaves open the question of where the decision to produce these coinages lay (“of what kind and when . . . of high and low value,” ποῖον καὶ πότε τίμιον ἢ εὐώνον) and with whose resources they were made. If, as seems to be the case, the satraps had very limited ability to spend the king’s money without his permission, and presumably very limited resources of their own, these coinages were effectively royal in origin, if not in immediate agency. As Bodzek notes, what mattered was the immediacy of the expression of power and authority, and for this the involvement of the man on the ground—satrap, dynast, *karanos*—was crucial.

That said, there is admittedly a much broader range of coinages that have to be considered than simply the “royal” and the apparently “satrapal.” In this respect, the paper by Ellis-Evans and Kagan (178–227) throws down a gauntlet. For them, there is certainly a powerful central monetary authority within the Achaemenid state; but they choose to read ps.-Aristotle’s description of the Great King’s interest in the value of the coinage in terms, in part at least, of monetary metals. Positing the use of gold as a fixed measure of value within the imperial space, they chart the fluctuations in weight of various silver coinages within the empire as reactions to the fluctuating prices of gold and silver against each other. They conclude by suggesting that this is the result essentially of an inflexible central insistence on the primacy of gold alongside a *laissez-faire* attitude to the production of silver within the empire. With regard to the monetary phenomena to which they draw attention, this creates a major new interpretative framework for the study of the metrology of coinage within (and outside of) imperial space. But whether we can be certain of the agency behind the individual decisions remains, perhaps, a subject for debate.

What we present within this volume is, then, the beginnings of a dialogue on the nature and role of coinage in imperial space. Much work remains to be done in this period, and in others, but some limited conclusions may perhaps be

offered here. Evidence from later periods suggests the need to be aware of the existence of “pseudo”-coinages, i.e., coinages that purport to be issued by one authority, but which may in fact have been produced with the tacit authority, and quite probably the bullion resources, of a higher power. Did this happen as early as the time of ps.-Aristotle in the fourth century B.C.E.? Did it happen earlier? And could this be part of the reason why he situates coinage with the realm of the “royal economy” and no other? A compelling case is made by de Callatay (45–69) for a substantial phenomenon of Achaemenid pseudo-coinage along the southern coast of Asia Minor, and further enquiry will be needed to explore whether this can be observed elsewhere. On the other hand, examination of the so-called “satrapal coinages” by Bodzek (70–121) yields no firm evidence as to the ultimate authority or financing of these issues. Taken at face value (iconography and legends), these appear to be satrapal. But the problem we encounter is whether such statements can be taken at face value. Elsewhere, it seems clear, there is little incontrovertible evidence for independent civic production within the Achaemenid empire. Documentary evidence (Duyrat, 228–249) suggests that much economic activity at this level and below might well have taken place without any coin production at all. The text of ps.-Aristotle may seem “primitive” to us, but that may well be because the monetary organisation of the world he was describing was “primitive” too.

NEW COLLEGE
 OXFORD OX1 3BN
 U.K.

andrew.meadows@new.ox.ac.uk

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